

Table 2. Grain quality features of promising Basmati restorers and maintainers.^a

Genotype	Aroma ^b	Before cooking			After cooking				
		Grain length (mm)	Grain breadth (mm)	L-B ratio	Grain length (mm)	Grain breadth (mm)	L-B ratio	Elongation ratio	Alkali value
Basmati 385	1	6.6	1.7	3.9	11.9	2.7	4.4	1.8	4.0
Chandan	1	7.3	1.8	4.1	12.4	3.5	3.5	1.7	4.0
P1031-8-5-1-1	1	8.2	1.8	4.6	16.4	2.5	6.6	2.0	5.0
HKR241-IET-12020	1	7.5	1.7	4.4	12.8	3.0	4.3	1.7	4.0
S.A.F. Khalsa 7	1	7.4	1.8	4.1	15.6	2.6	6.0	2.1	4.0
Karnal Local	1	7.3	1.7	4.3	13.9	3.6	3.9	1.9	4.0
HKR46	2	5.5	1.7	3.2	8.3	1.9	4.4	1.5	6.0
P1173-2-1	1	5.5	1.7	3.2	8.3	2.4	3.5	1.5	1.0
P1173-4-1	2	5.5	1.7	3.2	8.8	2.8	3.1	1.6	1.0
P615-K-167-13	2	6.4	1.7	3.8	12.2	2.5	4.9	1.9	7.0
Hasan Sarai	2	0.7	1.8	4.5	12.1	1.9	6.4	1.8	4.0
Basmati 370	1	6.9	1.8	3.8	12.4	2.1	5.9	1.8	4.0
Pusa Basmati 1	2	7.2	1.8	4.0	14.4	2.2	6.5	2.0	6.0

^aData pooled over 2 replications. ^b1 = strong; 2 = moderate.

Basmati 385, Chandan, and HKR241-IET-12020 were found to be effective restorers for IR58025 A, PMS10 A, and PMS3 A; P1031-8-5-1-1 for IR62829 A, PMS10 A, and PMS3 A; Karnal Local and HKR46 for IR58025 A and PMS10

A, and S.A.F. Khalsa 7 for PMS10 A (Table 1).

Basmati 370 and Pusa Basmati 1 were found to be effective maintainers for the four CMS lines; P1173-4-1 for IR58025 A, PMS10 A, and PMS3 A; and P615-K-

167-13 for PMS10 A and PMS3 A.

The performance of the restorers varied with CMS line, location, and season of testing. The differential ability to restore fertility in the CMS lines, which all have the wild abortive (WA) cyto sterile system, could be because of the influence of the different nuclear backgrounds of the CMS lines.

Among the restorers, Basmati 385, Chandan, P1031-8-5-1-1, HKR241-IET-12020, S.A.F. Khalsa 7, and Karnal Local possess acceptable grain dimensions and desirable degree of aroma and volume expansion through linear kernel elongation (Table 2). Similarly, among the maintainers, P615-K-167-13, Pusa Basmati 1, and Basmati 370 have acceptable grain and cooking quality characteristics for Basmati rice. These genotypes will contribute to developing Basmati hybrids and provide restorers and maintainers with acceptable key Basmati quality characteristics. ■

Identifying maintainers and restorers for three cytoplasmic male sterile lines of rice

Yog Raj and M. P. Pandey, Plant Breeding and Genetics Department, G.B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology (GBPUAT), Pantnagar 263145; and A. Kumar, Genetics Division, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi 110012, India

In hybrid rice breeding programs based on a cytoplasmic genetic male sterility system, identifying effective maintainers and restorers is important.

We crossed cytoplasmic male sterile lines (CMS) V20 A, Zhen Shan 97 A (ZS97 A), and IR46830 A, which all possess wild abortive (WA) cytoplasm, with 18 varieties and elite lines in a line × tester design at the Crop Research Centre, (CRC), GPUAT. The 54 hybrids and their parents were transplanted in two 3-m rows at 20- x 20-cm spacing during 1991 wet season (WS).

Five plants were randomly selected and used for analyzing pollen and spikelet fertility. About 10 spikelets, representing the upper, middle, and lower portions of half emerging panicles, were collected and squashed in 2.2% IKI stain to observe pollen fertility.

Fertility reaction^a of F₁ hybrids involving 3 CMS lines at CRC, Pantnagar, India. 1991 WS.

Variety/elite line	CMS line		
	V20 A	ZS97 A	IR46830 A
Narendra 118	PR	PR	PR
Kasturi	M	PM	M
UPR79-11	R	PR	R
N22	M	PR	PR
Rasi	PR	R	PM
Govind	R	R	PR
IR36	R	R	PR
UPR79-123	R	R	R
BG367-4	PM	PM	R
Pant Dhan 4	M	PR	PM
Sarju 52	R	PR	PM
Pusa 205	PR	PR	R
Suweon 294	R	PR	R
Suweon 325	R	R	R
Manhar	R	R	PM
Pusa 702	R	R	PM
Suweon 332	R	R	R
UPR231-28-1-2	R	PR	PR

^aR = restorer (60-100% pollen fertility, 80-100% spikelet fertility), PR = partial restorer (30-60% pollen fertility, 30-80% spikelet fertility), PM = partial maintainer (1-30% pollen and spikelet fertility), and M = maintainer (<1% pollen and spikelet fertility).

Restorers and maintainers identified were usually different for the three CMS lines (see table). Suweon 325, Suweon 332, and UPR79-123 consistently restored fertility of all the CMS lines. Some other restorers found promising were UPR79-11, Govind, IR36, Sarju 52, Suweon 294, Manhar, Pusa 702, and UPR231-28-1-2 for V20 A; Rasi, Govind, IR36, Manhar,

and Pusa 702 for ZS 97 A; and UPR79-11, BG367-4, Pusa 205, and Suweon 294 for IR46830 A. Maintainers identified were Kasturi, N22, and Pant Dhan 4 for V20 A and Kasturi for IR56830 A. The frequency of restorers (48.1%) was higher than that of maintainers (7.4%). We are using the promising restorers and maintainers in our hybrid rice breeding program. ■